

Synthesis of Purine Derivatives from Glyoxalines.

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The synthesis of purine derivatives has been hitherto accomplished mainly *via* pyrimidines. The alternative process of synthesis *via* glyoxaline was first suggested by Windaus and Knoop (*Hofmeister's Beiträge zur chemischen Physiologie und Pathologie*, 1905, 6, 392) in connection with the formation of methylimidazole by the action of ammonia (or zinc hydroxide-ammonia) on grape sugar and also other sugars. They write 'Gelingt es, die Methylgruppe (des Methylimidazols) zu oxidieren und eine Kondensation z.B. mit Harnstoff zu erzielen so erhielte man direct Xanthin. Andere Paarlinge wie Guanidin könnten in gleicher Weise zu Guanin, Hypoxanthin usw. führen.'

Johnson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36, 338) tried to prepare purines from glyoxalines or hydantoins but without success.

Speaking before the London Chemical Society on "Newer stand-points in the Theory of Nutrition" Hopkins compared the structure of arginine and histidine with that of the purine base guanine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 629); and pointed to some experiments which prove that the presence or absence respectively of *arginine and histidine* from

the food of an animal has a very considerable effect on purine metabolism as indicated by allantoin excretion. there being a very marked fall as the result of their withdrawal whilst their restoration is followed by a rise.*

Fargher and Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 217) attempted to prepare 4-aminoglyoxaline-5-carboxylic acid with a view to obtain

* In a subsequent communication (*Biochem. J.*, 1916, 10, 551) Ackroyd and Hopkins have demonstrated that the absence of one or the other is without any apparent effect on growth.

xanthine by condensing the substance with cyanic acid and subsequently eliminating water. They failed, however, to prepare the amino-acid.

With the same object in view, King and Murch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 621) prepared ethyl 4-bromoglyoxaline-5-carboxylate, but the small yield precluded systematic attempts to condense the ester with carbamide.

A purine-derivative, heteroxanthine, was first prepared by Sarasin and Wegmann (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, 7, 713) by heating the amide of 4-amino-1-methylglyoxaline-5-carboxylic acid with ethyl carbonate at 160-70°. Plaza (*Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1926, 24, 731) employed the same reaction for the preparation of 8-methyl-7-ethylxanthine from 4-amino-2-methyl-1-ethylglyoxaline-5-carboxylamide. Montequi (*Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1927, 25, 182) obtained 8-methyl-7-ethylxanthine and also heteroxanthine by heating 5-cyano-4-amino-2-methyl-1-ethylglyoxaline and 5-cyano-4-amino-1-methylglyoxaline respectively with urethane.

On an analysis of the mechanism of these reactions we find that in both the cases, eight out of the nine members constituting the purine skeleton are present in the starting material chosen while the ninth member, consisting of a carbon atom, is introduced subsequently between two N atoms. Not only do the reactions take place at high temperatures but it is difficult to imagine a simple reaction likely to take place in nature, giving rise to a substance containing the requisite carbon-nitrogen framework.

The difficulty is obviated when we recall the observations of Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 669) that diaminoacetone dihydrochloride gives by the action of potassium thiocyanate 2-thiol-4 (or 5)-amino-

methylglyoxaline and 2-thiol-4 (or 5)-thiocarbamidomethylglyoxaline.

It will be observed that the substance contains the purine skeleton and a similar reaction between diaminoacetone and cyanic acid is quite likely to lead to the formation of purine derivatives in nature.

We have been strengthened in our supposition as we have been able to realise the scheme outlined above, though in a somewhat modified form.

When 4 (or 5)-aminomethylglyoxaline hydrochloride (Pyman, *loc. cit.*) is brominated in hydrobromic acid solution, 2:4-dibromo-5-aminomethylglyoxaline (II) is obtained in solution, while a tribromo compound, apparently the bromoamine, is precipitated. The filtrate on basifying gives (II) which on treatment with potassium thiocyanate gives (III) which readily undergoes ring-closure with the formation of a substance (IV) containing a fused thiazoline-glyoxaline ring.

If, however, the product is first methylated and then digested in alcoholic solution with pyridine, ring formation takes place in the desired manner with the formation of a purine derivative (2-methyl-mercapto-8-bromo-1.6-dihydropurine).

EXPERIMENTAL.

2:4-Dibromo-5-aminomethylglyoxaline.—5(or 4)-Aminomethylglyoxaline hydrochloride (1 g.), prepared according to the method of Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 668, 2172), was dissolved in water (20 c.c.) and 3 c.c. of 36% hydrobromic acid added. To the solution, bromine was added (0.6 c.c.) drop by drop, when a light yellow crystalline product (0.14 g.) separated. It is a tribromo compound, m.p. 214°. (Found: N, 12.9. $C_4H_4N_3Br_3$ requires N, 12.5 per cent).

The tribromo compound was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness on the water-bath, dissolved in water and neutralised with dilute potassium carbonate solution. The precipitate after recrystallisation from water melts with decomposition at 230°. (Found: C, 18.4; H, 2.0; N, 16.1; Br, 62.2. $C_4H_5N_3Br_2$ requires C, 18.8; H, 1.9; N, 16.4; Br, 62.7 per cent).

2:4-Dibromo-5-thiocarbamidomethylglyoxaline—Potassium thiocyanate (0.16 g.) was dissolved in a small quantity of hot water and the calculated amount of 2:4-dibromo-5-aminomethylglyoxaline gradually added. The mixture was heated on the water-bath for about 2 hours, cooled and filtered. After repeated crystallisation from water a crystalline mass was obtained, m.p. 252° (decomp.). (Found: C, 18.8; H, 1.9; N, 17.6. $C_5H_6N_4Br_2S$ requires C, 19.1; H, 1.9; N, 17.8 per cent).

2:4-Dibromo-5-methylthiocarbamidomethylglyoxaline.—Methylation was effected by moistening the finely powdered mercaptan with alcohol and then adding the calculated quantity of methyl iodide to it. It was shaken well and allowed to stand overnight. It was then

filtered and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 220° (decomp.). (Found: N, 16.6. $C_6H_8N_4Br_2S$ requires N, 17.0 per cent).

2-Methylmercapto-8-bromo-1:6-dihydropurine.—The methylated product was taken up in absolute alcohol and heated on the water-bath under reflux with the addition of a small quantity of pyridine for 5 hours. The alcohol was evaporated and the process repeated. The product was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $198-200^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 22.4. $C_6H_7N_4BrS$ requires N, 22.6 per cent.). It gives the murexide reaction.

Thiazolinoglyoxaline derivative was obtained by refluxing 2:4-dibromo-5-thiocarbamidomethylglyoxaline in alcohol with a small quantity of pyridine. Nodules from dilute alcohol, m.p. 165° . (Found: N, 23.8. $C_5H_5N_4BrS$ requires N, 24.0 per cent).

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